

Cultural Diversity among the Employees and its Effect in Organizational Climate

Dr. G. Balamurugan¹, B. Santhiya²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Management Studies, Anna University(BIT Campus), Tiruchirappalli, INDIA

²PG Student, Department of Management Studies, Anna University(BIT Campus), Tiruchirappalli, INDIA

¹Corresponding Author: drgbalamuruganmba@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Cultural diversity is a group of diverse individuals from different cultures or societies. The study is conducted to explore how manage workforce diversity and its consequences to the company's existence as well as examine how companies' deal with challenges that comes with employees from diverse cultural backgrounds. The study describe diversity challenges that can affect the working climate and conflict between the employees through the diversity .The result shows that cultural diversity plays an effective role in some companies however inadequate mentoring and guidance could cause a company low productivity. For this reason there is must be regular improvement in ways to effectively manage a cultural diverse in workforce as the world keeps advancing.

Keywords-- Cultural Diversity, Effect, Organizational Climate

I. INTRODUCTION

There are many areas discussed in the following papers on cultural diversity and its effect in organizational climate. Cultural diversity is important in a changing world. If our basic courses are to be current with student needs of the future, incorporating instruction on effectiveness within multicultural setting is important. Many organizations experience cross cultural management, based on the different culture, there may exist different management approaches, to adapt cultural diversity, adapt cultural environment ,improve employee satisfaction and so on. In addition, employee satisfaction can often be influenced by cultural diversity or ethnic diversity, every company has a corporate culture, and when the corporate culture, meets cultural diversity, it will have positive and negative influence on employee satisfaction. A positive organizational diversity climate will be intolerant of workplace harassment and discrimination, whereas a negative diversity climate will convey to employees that harassment and discrimination are tolerated by the organization. Since managing diversity still remains a challenge in organizations, managers tend to learn managerial skills needed in a multicultural working environment and prepares themselves to teach others within their organizations to value cultural differences and treat all employees with dignity.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To identify cultural diversity among the employees.
- To study the cultural challenges that can affect the working climate and find out conflicts between employees.
- To investigate the impact of cultural differences on team work in organisation.

III. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

- Martha kyrillidou and M.Sue Baughman, (2009): The survey addresses a number of climate issues, such as diversity, team work, learning and fairness as well as current managerial practices and staff attitudes and beliefs.
- Priscilla dike,(2013): The study is conducted to explore how companies deal with challenges that comes with employees from diverse cultural backgrounds.
- Saumya Goyal and Dr. Sangya Shrivastava,(2013): This study makes a healthy and happy working environment for all the categories of employees.
- Joel Augustus Daddie,(2015): Mismanaged diversity can cause employee dissatisfaction which can affect productivity, leading to lower job performance.

IV. CULTURAL DIVERSITY

Cultural diversity is the similarities and differences in such characteristics as age, gender, ethnic heritage, physical abilities and disabilities, race, sexual orientation among the employees of organizations. Employees conceptions of work, expectations of rewards, sufficient salary from the organization and practices in relating to others are all influenced by diversity.

Managers of diverse work groups in organization so must need to understand how the social environment affects employees norms and beliefs about work and they must have communication skills to develop confidence, relationship and self-esteem in members of diverse work groups.

Workforce diversity does not automatically result in positive outcomes. The reality is that increased

diversity can lead to increased conflict among organizational employees. Differential expectations and unspoken assumptions can cause conflicts and misunderstandings.

V. ADVANTAGES AND CHALLENGES OF CULTURAL DIVERSITY

Improved innovation based on the concept that differences will provide new and different ideas. Problem-solving is aided by staff with different perspectives, backgrounds and training.

Other benefits can include competitive edge, better public image, increased productivity, job satisfaction and morale, as well as improved inter staff relations and a satisfying work environment.

The Challenges of Cultural Diversity

- Diversity in unity-in-spite of belonging to one country each state has its own language.
- Most of the time community identity is ascribed status and you learn to love them.
- Different understandings of professional etiquette.
- Conflicting working styles across teams.

VI. INTRODUCTION TO ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE

Organizational climate is the shared perception of employees who work and live in the organization. It is the sum of individual perceptions regarding the organizational procedures, policies and practices. It represents the psychological environment of the organization consisting of individual opinions framed upon micro events that happen to them as well as to others around, over a period of time.

Organizational climate is an important concept because it is an influence on the behavior of organization members.

VII. IMPORTANCE OF ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE

Organizational climate is the manifestation of the attitudes of organizational members towards the organization itself.

- An organization tends to attract and keep people who fit its climate, so that its patterns are perpetuated at least to some extent.
- To facilitate measurement and manipulation of organizational climate, researchers have dissected its characteristics and perceptions into categories such as the nature of interpersonal relationships, the nature of the hierarchy, the nature of work, and the focus of support and rewards.

VIII. FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE

- ✓ Involvement
- ✓ Supervisor Support
- ✓ Autonomy
- ✓ Work Pressure
- ✓ Clarity

IX. MEASURING CLIMATE

Measurement of climate seeks to identify the components of both bad and good climate, both in absolute terms and perceptual terms. While there are commercial instruments that measure climate, there are powerful arguments for having one tailor made to the organization.

Generally, the areas of interest to measure are:

- External environment
- Organizational leadership
- Organizational structure
- Management practices

X. THE EFFECTS OF DIVERSITY IN THE WORKPLACE

- Solid research needed to be conducted to support the idea that diversity was beneficial to the workplace.
- Diversity was found to be a lot more complex than it was originally thought to be.
- Research indicates that diversity can produce both positive and negative when introduced and enforced in the workplace.
- Evidence suggests that diversity may produce conflict and employee turnover as well as more creativity and innovation.

Negative Effects of Diversity

- Diverse groups are shown to be less integrated and have a higher of dissatisfaction.
- Increases the level of dissatisfaction in group members, as well as miscommunication.
- Diversity can be linked with conflict, lower group adhesiveness, increased employee turnover and absenteeism, and lower quality of performance.

XI. DIVERSITY TRAINING

As diversity in the workplace grows at an amazing rate, more and more organizations are now focusing on diversity in the workplace by emphasizing recruitment, selection, retention and training.

- Diversity training objectives in the workplace:
- Increase awareness about diversity issues
- Define and describe the various issues related to diversity, equity, and inclusion in their

respective disciplines.

- The purpose of diversity training is to increase participants cultural awareness, knowledge and communication.
- Diversity training can benefit an organization by helping to prevent civil rights violations, increasing the inclusion of different identity groups, and promoting better teamwork.

Strategies

- Gain senior leadership commitment Engage employees in the process.
- Support local/community diversity groups
- Provide diversity training, not as the destination but as part of the journey.
- Promote open communication and dialogue.

XII. HOW TO OVERCOME CULTURAL BARRIERS AT WORK

- Ensure clear and polite communication
- Learn about different cultures
- Work towards accommodating cultural difference
- Share knowledge
- Employ diversity training

XIII. CONCLUSION

Cultural diversity is very important at workplace these days. As a manager, you have to understand the cultural diversity in every phase within organization. Finally, gives to equal rights to all employees this is cannot any effects arise in organization climate.

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